

Nonverbal rating scale of the Aasis project / 5.11.2024 AvZ

The scale has been translated by Ilona Lähteenmäki (2.12.2024)

In the Aasis project, spoken language skills refer to not only linguistic features (overall rating, range, accuracy, phonology, fluency, interaction) but also nonverbal features of spoken language.

--Speaker on the left--

Which of the following nonverbal features did you pay attention to in the speaker on the left? Did the feature support or hinder interaction?

Mark "+" if you think the feature supported interaction, "-" if the feature hindered interaction, "0" if the effect on interaction was neutral, "?" if you are not sure.

Facial expressions (e.g. smiling, raising the eyebrows) or lack of them

Eye contact or lack of it

Head movements (e.g. nodding) or lack of them

Sounds (e.g. yeah, mm, no way), laughter or lack of them

Hand movements (e.g. gestures, pointing) or lack of them

Other, please specify: [open field]

You can complete your answer or comment on the left speaker's nonverbal behaviour here

[big open field]

Do you think that the nonverbal features you saw in the dialogue affected your rating of the speaker's proficiency level?

Yes

No

I cannot comment

You can expand on your answer here (if needed, use the speaker's ID)

[open field]

-- Speaker on the right --

Which of the following nonverbal features did you pay attention to in the speaker on the right? Did the feature support or hinder interaction?

Mark "+" if you think the feature supported interaction, "-" if the feature hindered interaction, "0" if the effect on interaction was neutral, "?" if you are not sure.

Facial expressions (e.g. smiling, raising the eyebrows) or lack of them

Eye contact or lack of it

Head movements (e.g. nodding) or lack of them

Sounds (e.g. yeah, mm, no way), laughter or lack of them

Hand movements (e.g. gestures, pointing) or lack of them

Other, please specify: [open field]

You can complete your answer or comment on the right speaker's nonverbal behaviour here

[big open field]

Do you think that the nonverbal features you saw in the dialogue affected your rating of the speaker's proficiency level?

Yes

No

I cannot comment

You can explain your answer here (if needed, use the speaker's ID)

[open field]

-- Whole dialogue / both speakers --

After having watched the video of the dialogue performance, what kind of an overall impression do you have of the two speakers' interaction?

I think the interaction worked mainly without problems

I think there were problems in the interaction

I cannot comment

You can expand on your answer here (e.g. turn distribution, friendliness, differences in the speakers' proficiency levels, if needed, use the speakers' IDs to identify them)

[big open field]